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São Paulo, October 21, 2025.

Mr. Cláudio Alves da Silva
Arcos Dorados Comércio de Alimentos S/A.

Re: Memorandum of completion of work

Dear Cláudio, As agreed, we present our considerations regarding the support provided in the sample selection process of 60 (sixty) employees from the Arcos Dorados asset base, according to criteria previously defined by the Company.

We are available for any further clarifications that may be necessary.

Sincerely,
DELOITTE TOUCHE TOHMATSU CONSULTORES LTDA.

Claudia Martins Gomes
Sócia de Global Employer Services

I - Scope of Work

Our work consisted of supporting the sample selection of 60 (sixty) employees from the Arcos Dorados asset base, composed of approximately 20,000 records, according to criteria previously defined by the Company.

To carry out the activities, we used the Python programming language as a tool for executing the sample selection, applying the established criteria to the database provided by Arcos Dorados, in Excel format, which included all active registrations up to the cutoff date of October 7, 2025.

Scope Limitations

The sample selection services for Arcos Dorados employees were conducted based on data and information previously structured by the Company itself, and the sufficiency and reliability of this data were essential for the completion of the project.

II – Work Development

Based on the data provided by Arcos Dorados on October 7, 2025, we used the Python programming language as a tool for sample selection, in accordance with the criteria previously established by the Company itself.

The sample consisted of 60 registrations, selected according to the following criteria:

- **Generation Range:** 1 employee from the Baby Boomer generation, 2 employees from Generation X, 15 employees from Generation Y, and 42 employees from Generation Z.
- **Biological Sex:** 33 female employees and 27 male employees.
- **Person with Disability:** 2 employees with disabilities.
- **Race/Color:** 1 employee of Asian descent, 19 employees of Caucasian descent, 27 employees of mixed race, 11 employees of Black descent, 1 employee of Indigenous ethnicity, and 1 employee with race or ethnicity not reported.
- **Employee Group:** 43 employees from the “Crew” group, 2 employees from Management, 12 employees from the “Swing” group, 2 employees from Maintenance, and 1 employee from Operations.

It is important to highlight that employees who were absent for any reason (vacation, medical leave, maternity leave, retirement, among others), as well as those hired less than six months ago, were excluded from the database.

III – Results

We conducted a structured process to select a representative sample of employees, based on minimum criteria, as detailed in the previous section. Our goal was to ensure that this sample adequately reflected the composition of the workforce, considering the aspects most relevant to the research.

The analysis began with the extraction of data from an Excel spreadsheet provided by Arcos Dorados. In the preparation stage, standardization routines were applied to ensure the

consistency of the information, such as the standardization of nomenclature (e.g., use of capital letters) and the removal of blank spaces.

Next, the minimum representativeness criteria, defined directly by the Company, were applied without the use of statistical methods. The attributes considered included generational range, race/color, employment group, biological sex, and disability status.

The sample was constructed iteratively, with the goal of fully meeting the established criteria. Finally, the sample was validated to ensure compliance with all defined criteria. Multiple combination attempts were made until a set was obtained that fully met the established requirements, as demonstrated in the selection presented below.

Amostra	Matrícula	Geração	Raça	Grupo Empregados	Sexo	Deficiência
1	60031824	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Não
2	2211932	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
3	60044413	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Masculino	Não
4	60034071	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Masculino	Não
5	2249048	Geração Z	Parda	Manutenção	Masculino	Não
6	60085641	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
7	60103711	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
8	60107930	Geração Y	Branca	Crew	Masculino	Sim
9	2339006	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
10	60094975	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
11	2267192	Geração Z	Parda	Swing	Feminino	Não
12	60073042	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
13	2337437	Geração Z	Branca	Swing	Feminino	Não
14	2312730	Geração Y	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
15	60104325	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Não
16	105351	Geração Y	Branca	Gerência	Masculino	Não
17	60083245	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
18	2263115	Geração Z	Parda	Swing	Masculino	Não
19	424520	Geração Y	Preta	Crew	Masculino	Não
20	60096576	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
21	359423	Geração Y	Branca	Swing	Feminino	Não

<i>Amostra</i>	<i>Matrícula</i>	<i>Geração</i>	<i>Raça</i>	<i>Grupo Empregados</i>	<i>Sexo</i>	<i>Deficiência</i>
22	60089872	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Masculino	Não
23	60113489	Geração Y	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
24	60102444	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
25	12223731	Geração X	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Sim
26	60112493	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
27	60084834	Geração Y	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
28	60097882	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
29	10415502	Geração X	Branca	Swing	Feminino	Não
30	324084	Geração Y	Branca	Swing	Masculino	Não
31	2337365	Geração Z	Sem Informação	Swing	Masculino	Não
32	60054676	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Masculino	Não
33	444794	Geração Y	Branca	Gerência	Feminino	Não
34	2222286	Geração Z	Parda	Swing	Masculino	Não
35	60084499	Geração Y	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Sim
36	60041721	Geração X	Parda	Manutenção	Masculino	Não
37	60020089	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Não
38	60107163	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
39	60110447	Geração X	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
40	60049886	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
41	60114065	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
42	60069993	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Masculino	Não
43	60103365	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Não
44	340618	Geração Y	Preta	G&A	Masculino	Não
45	60087805	Geração Y	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
46	521724	Geração Y	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
47	60096137	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
48	60015263	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
49	514992	Geração Y	Parda	Swing	Feminino	Não
50	60092831	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
51	60062128	Geração Z	Preta	Crew	Feminino	Não
52	282479	Geração Y	Indigena	Swing	Masculino	Não
53	60042050	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Feminino	Não
54	60056272	Geração Z	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Não
55	60115272	Geração X	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Não
56	2215296	Geração Y	Parda	Crew	Masculino	Sim
57	434679	Geração Y	Parda	Gerência	Masculino	Não
58	12160121	Geração Z	Branca	Swing	Masculino	Não
59	60083985	Geração Z	Branca	Crew	Feminino	Não
60	60084051	Geração Z	Amarela	Crew	Feminino	Não

The data analysis demonstrated compliance with most of the established criteria. However, inconsistencies were identified in the following categories: Baby Boomer generation (shortage of one employee), Generation Z (shortage of four employees), and the "Swing" employee group (shortage of one employee). The remaining criteria were fully met, with no deviations from the defined parameters.

IV – Deliverables

In conclusion to our work, we provide the following documents:

- Advisory Memorandum (this document); and
- Excel file containing the consolidation of the data collected, organized according to the categories previously defined by Arcos Dorados.

These being the comments we deemed pertinent to formalize, we remain available for further clarification.

Sincerely,
DELOITTE TOUCHE TOHMATSU CONSULTORES LTDA.

Claudia Martins Gomes
Partner at Global Employer Services